

CHEMISTRY OF ALIPHATIC THIOCARBAMIDES. PART V. N:N:N'-TRIMETHYLTHIOCARBAMIDE

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Chemistry of N:N:N'-trimethylthiocarbamide has been investigated with respect to its formation and interaction with acids, alkalies, desulphurising agents, silver nitrate, bromine, iodine, nitrous acid, acetic anhydride and benzyl chloride.

N:N:N'-Trimethylthiocarbamide was prepared by the condensation of methyl mustard oil and dimethylamine according to Hofmann's procedure (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1874, 17, 72). A general examination of the chemistry of this compound has been undertaken.

In its behaviour towards hydrolytic reagents, it resembles other aliphatic thiocarbamides (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 499, 695; 1954, 31, 355, 628), although it is more stable. Since it lacks the necessary number of potentially mobile hydrogens, it is not desulphurised with the usual desulphiding agents like mercuric oxide, alkaline lead acetate, etc. (Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 318). When boiled with a strong solution of sodium zincate, however, zinc sulphide is formed in considerable quantity. With aqueous silver nitrate it forms complex compounds, where four or five molecules of silver nitrate combine with two or three molecules of trimethylthiocarbamide. Depending on the relative quantities of the reactants and the experimental conditions, higher or lower complexes are obtained (vide Experimental). Like other aliphatic thiocarbamides, on oxidation with bromine and other oxidising agents it forms the corresponding 'formamidine disulphide' salt. With acetic anhydride and benzyl chloride in the usual way, N-acetyl and S-benzyl derivatives respectively are obtained (cf. Dixon and Hawthorne, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 128, 144).

EXPERIMENTAL

Formation.—Methyl mustard oil (36 g.) and dimethylamine (25 g.) were condensed in alcohol medium. The residue after evaporating off the alcohol was crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 87°, yield 53 g. corresponding to 90%. (Found: N, 23.69; S, 27.0. $C_4H_{10}N_2S$ requires N, 23.73; S, 27.11 per cent). The molecular weight was determined cryoscopically using water as the solvent; 0.436 g. of the substance in 25 c.c., 30 c.c. and 35 c.c. water recorded depression of 0.265°, 0.230° and 0.19° respectively, corresponding with molecular weights 118.74, 113.7 and 118.7.

Hydrolysis.—Trimethylthiocarbamide (1.18 g.) was heated under reflux for 1 hour with 25 c.c. of N and 5N sulphuric acid and caustic soda solutions. The decomposition products were estimated as in other cases (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 499). Only 5N-NaOH could decompose it to the extent of affording 43% amine and 41% H_2S .

Desulphurisation.—Trimethylthiocarbamide (0.118 g. in 100 c.c. water) was heated on a water-bath with potassium zincate solution (10 c.c.) for half an hour at 60°, 80° and 100°. After filtering off the zinc sulphide formed, the remaining thiocarbamide in the filtrate was estimated by titrating against Hg(NO₃)₂ solution after acidifying it with dilute HNO₃ (*ibid.*, 1953, 30, 223; 1954, 31, 355). % Desulphurisation at 60°, 80° and 100° was 0%, 0% and 5.5% respectively.

Reaction with Silver Nitrate.—Aqueous solutions of trimethylthiocarbamide and silver nitrate of various concentrations were mixed at room temperature, at boiling point and at 0°. The results are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Complex compounds of trimethylthiocarbamide and silver nitrate.

S. No.	AgNO ₃ :Thi.	AgNO ₃	Wt. of Thi.	Condi- tion of reaction.	Ag-salt ignited.	Ag reco- vered.	Loss.	Ag: loss.		Composi- tion.
								Pound.	Calc.	
1	1:1	0.725 g.	0.30 g.	Cold	0.3584 g.	0.1484 g.	0.2100 g.	432:604.8	432:602	3Thi.4AgNO ₃
	"	"	"	"	0.4116	0.1728	0.3288	432:596.8	"	"
2	2:1	0.85	0.30	"	0.2844	0.1188	0.1656	432:602.8	"	"
	"	3.40	1.18	"	0.4674	0.1966	0.2708	432:594.8	"	"
	"	"	"	"	0.3258	0.1356	0.1902	432:602.8	"	"
3	1:2	0.425	0.59	"	0.0622	0.0264	0.0358	432:586.0	"	"
	"	"	"	"	0.1898	0.0784	0.1114	432:514.0	"	"
	"	0.85	1.18	"	0.6374	0.2680	0.3694	432:595.6	"	"
	"	"	"	"	0.4720	0.1998	0.2522	432:588.4	"	"
4	4:1	1.7	0.30	"	0.3970	0.1566	0.2004	540:546.0	540:546	2Thi.5AgNO ₃
5	1:4	0.425	1.18	"	No precipitate was obtained.					
6	1:1			Boiling	"	"	"			
7	1:2			"	"	"	"			
8	2:1			"	"	"	"			
9	1:1			0°	0.5304	0.2320	0.2984	540:694.5	540:664	3Thi.5AgNO ₃
10	4:1			"	0.3618	0.1804	0.1814	540:543.6	540:546	2Thi.5AgNO ₃

Oxidation.—Equivalent quantities of trimethylthiocarbamide and bromine (both dissolved in chloroform) were mixed. A yellow sticky mass separated which under alcohol became colorless but retained its sticky nature. It could not be obtained in a crystalline form. Its picrate was also sticky. It liberated iodine from aqueous potassium iodide. With alkali it decomposed affording sulphur (cf. 'formamidine disulphide', Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2166, 2180).

Nitrous Acid Interaction.—Trimethylthiocarbamide (3 g.) and 15 c.c. of 5N acetic acid were taken in a beaker and cooled in ice. Ice-cooled normal sodium nitrite solution (50 c.c.) was added gradually. An oily liquid separated which being highly unstable could not be further purified. It is presumably (CH₃)₂N.CS.N(NO)CH₃.

N-Acetyl Derivative.—Trimethylthiocarbamide (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (4 c.c.) were heated along with a little zinc chloride for about 10 minutes, and poured in

water. A white crystalline solid separated which was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 154°. [Found: N, 17.3; S, 20.2. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}.\text{CS}.\text{N}(\text{COCH}_3)\text{CH}_3$ requires N, 17.5; S, 20.0 per cent].

S-Benzyl Derivative.—Equivalent quantities of trimethylthiocarbamide and benzyl chloride were warmed in 40% alcohol and left on a watch glass. Colorless massive crystals separated, m.p. 146-48°. [Found: N, 13.2; S, 15.15. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 13.35; S, 15.31 per cent].

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